

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DIOMELLA MARIE P. ORACION

TEACHER I / MAED STUDENT

BAGONG PAG-ASA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL / GREENVILLE COLLEGE

diomellamarie.pagado@deped.gov.ph

“CULTIVATING A CULTURE OF TRUST AND INTEGRITY IN SCHOOLS—STARTS WITH US”

“A school is not just a place of education; it is a trust center and a life system where the values of equity, reliability, and integrity are demonstrated through leadership.”

It is often said that education is crucial to the growth of our country. But how fundamental is education in helping the Philippines grow, and what other things should we pay attention to? Philippine school governance administers the school as a unit by supervising its functions, including the finances, students, and the human resources, which are the teachers. Utilizing ethical governance in schools is ensuring that every child, regardless of their background, has open access to quality education. Good school governance is fundamental not only for the organizations of schools but also for the long-term progress of our society. This also helps enforce the policies that fight discrimination and promote fairness and transparency for everyone.

When it comes to the running of schools, we should have ethical leadership and transparency, wherein it is a requirement. So what does it mean to be ethical? To be ethical is to do what is just and right in every situation. The principal and heads of each department have their roles to play in being fair to everybody. For example, when teaching loads and coordinators are assigned, or when it is decided who gets access to certain scholarship programs for students, we should see to it that such decisions are based on transparent and fair criteria, rather than personal relationships or politics. Though sometimes in practice, we often see that decisions are made in favor of certain individuals, which, of course, benefits them, and this leads to issues of unfair play, disappointment, and unhappy behavior that is evident between the students and teachers.

On the other hand, when we discuss transparency, it means being open and easy to understand. A transparent school keeps everyone informed, where the teachers, parents, and students know the school's goals. They also have the freedom to openly share information and decisions with each other. This way, it helps everyone understand what the plans are or the latest happenings in the school, making it easier to solve problems and misunderstandings, which results in trusting one another, ensuring decisions are fair, equal, and honest.

One example of transparency is the School-Based Management (SBM), where the principal holds meetings with parents, teachers, and community members to discuss the school's programs and budget. A student who is attending a transparent school will be getting more support because everyone is working towards

improving their education. A school that does not practice transparency will likely abuse the allotted resources.

Note that there are some schools that also practice SBM, but transparency was not their prior practice. What may be the reason behind this? Some of the reasons are lack of communication regarding school affairs, bias towards certain students, ambiguous spending, and unilaterally decided budget cuts without proper justification.

However, the given issues can be easily resolved by these suggestions: Having public forums, a school Facebook page, or a parent group chat in which to discuss what the school's plans are and where they are putting the budget. Additionally, we should see to it that principals and teachers are trained not just in the school's rules but in how they should interact and help out in our community because consequently, the school will develop strong ties with parents and local authorities. Of all the elements in our education system, the future of the students is our main focus. For our education system to truly serve the Filipino people, we must see to it that our schools are run by strong values instead of just rules.

On the whole note, schools are not just a place for academic learning and gaining knowledge but also a place where students learn about values, character development, personality, and behavior. Having good governance ensures that all of the actions and decisions being planned and made are open to everyone and are guided by clear intentions so the budget will not be corrupted, power will not be abused, and there will be no discrimination. This, then, points out how important ethics and open school governance are. As an educational management major, I have witnessed the enormous impact of even the smallest leadership decisions; they make a big effect on the entire school community. To cultivate a culture of trust, inclusion, and integrity in school, we must first model these values ourselves. Real change starts with responsible leadership—and it starts with us.